

**MULTIMODAL DEEP LEARNING FOR PULMONARY DISEASE CLASSIFICATION: A
DEPLOYMENT-ORIENTED FRAMEWORK FOR HEALTHCARE AND SOCIAL GOOD**

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Abstract: Globally, pulmonary diseases are a major health burden, especially in settings where resources are constrained and access to specialized radiological expertise is limited. Most chest radiograph-based deep learning models rely only on imaging data, despite showing promising performance when it comes to their diagnostic capabilities. However, clinical decision-making in the real world integrates structured patient information with the aforementioned imaging data. Our study aims to compare current multimodal machine learning approaches that combine clinical data and imaging used in pulmonary disease classification and propose a deployable framework designed for clinical settings in resource-constrained environments.

We conducted a review of recent literature around multimodal AI in pulmonary diseases, and we focused on fusion strategies (early-stage, late-stage, and hybrid), techniques for data integration, validation settings, as well as deployment considerations. We performed a comparative synthesis aiming to identify methodological patterns, translational gaps, and performance trends, and based on which we proposed a modular architecture integrating structured-data encoders with convolutional neural networks for imaging data, and fusion mechanisms to handle incomplete modalities.

This review indicates that multimodal approaches consistently outperform unimodal imaging models, especially in early-stage or complex cases, with gains in performance reported across many pulmonary conditions. However, the review also reveals several limitations, whether it's the lack of standardized fusion evaluation, insufficiencies in external validation, inadequacies in the handling of missing clinical variables, or limited attention to real-world clinical integration. These obstacles expose the need for system design that is deployment-aware more so than solely performance-driven optimization.

Through this work, we aim to contribute a structured synthesis of multimodal pulmonary AI and provide an interpretable and scalable framework suitable for integration into healthcare workflows, while remaining resource-conscious. By aligning the model design philosophy with the realities of clinical workflows, this approach should support equitable access to AI-assisted diagnostics and help advance the application of AI for healthcare improvement and social good.

Keywords : Artificial intelligence, Pulmonary disease, Classification, Multimodal, Medical imaging, Clinical data